

COMMENTING IN A SCHOOL WITH A NON-RUSSIAN LANGUAGE OF INSTRUCTION

Ayupov Timur Rustamovich.

Senior Lecturer, Kokand State Pedagogical Institute named after Mukimiy,
Uzbekistan, Kokand.

ANNOTATION The specificity of studying Russian literature in national schools determines the originality of teaching methods and techniques. Mastering the artistic, moral and ethical wealth of Russian literature in a national school is associated with significant difficulties, which are associated, on the one hand, with the vocabulary and phraseological support of the Russian literature course, on the other hand, with the specifics of national literature, the remoteness of the social and cultural-historical era of works from modern reader. In this regard, the scope and use of commented reading in the national school is significantly expanding.

Key words: Russian literature, national literature, work of art, phenomenon of national culture, national environment, lexicon M.D. Kocherin, G.I. Belenky, M.A. Shneerson, OK. Bogomolov.

In this article we will rely on the manual by L.A. Sheiman “Fundamentals of methods of teaching literature in the Kyrgyz school”.

The perception of a work of art is a kind of co-creation between the writer and the reader, which requires a certain life experience, mental and emotional development in the imagination of students. The national environment, which is the source of the student’s life experience, consists of the characteristics of everyday life, moral ideas, norms of behavior, phenomena of national culture, and art.

“When reading literary works in Russian for the first time, foreign-language students, often influenced by the habits of fluent reading in their native language, do not think about the meaning of individual words. Practice shows that independent reading (without the help of a teacher) of a Russian text can be inaccurate, so familiarization with the text of a work of art must be prepared: some difficult

linguistic phenomena and realities that make it difficult to perceive the text must first be introduced into the lexicon; the teacher should carefully comment on the beginning of the work or read it himself and check how well the students understand it. Sometimes the teacher's commentary should accompany not only the beginning of the work. However, one should not overuse commenting; one should only explain what the students will not understand without the help of the teacher. Therefore, commenting requires great skill from the teacher and should pursue broad goals, and not be reduced, as it happens, to familiarization with the content of the work” [1. p. 132-134].

«... In the process of studying Russian literature in a national school, students’ path to a deep perception and comprehension of the art of words encounters many obstacles due to the presence of little-known proper names, outdated vocabulary, and outdated everyday realities. All these difficulties are aggravated in the national school due to insufficient familiarity with Russian history, culture, and the realities of Russian life... » [1. p. 9].

For example, it is often difficult for a Kyrgyz schoolchild to perceive and understand works of Russian literature due to the unusual ethnographic details, some unfamiliarity with social relations, and customs. Sometimes the student is unfamiliar not only with the word, but also with the very phenomenon or object that it denotes (for example, Anna Ioannovna, a frock coat, a cellar, etc.).

The aesthetic perception of works of art is also based in the national school on ideas associated with geographical and ethnic features that surround a person since childhood. This is precisely what determines the entire “figurative arsenal” (M.V. Cherkezova) of the literature of a given people - the entire traditionally established system of figurative means. The perception of foreign literature is further complicated by the fact that its primary element is a language that is not native to students. Thus, in a national school, two obstacles arise on the path to familiarization with the spiritual values of Russian fiction in the conditions of a national school - language and cultural-aesthetic barriers.

The task of teaching Russian literature is to find ways to overcome these difficulties. A system of techniques and methods for analyzing a work of art is designed to solve this problem, among which the decisive role belongs to commented reading.

“A teacher of a national school must imagine how a student of a given age will perceive the unique world of the works of a particular writer, must help correlate this world with the knowledge and aesthetic skills that students have developed in the process of studying their native literature, that is, when studying Russian literature has the place and positive influence of the aesthetic experience of students acquired in Kyrgyz literature lessons” [4. p. 192].

Consequently, one of the important methods of organizing commented reading in a school with a non-Russian language of instruction is the support of those skills and abilities that students receive in the course of their native literature, and the use of the knowledge acquired by students when becoming acquainted with the phenomena of their native literature, which are close in ideological and artistic terms to certain phenomena of Russian literature.

Story by A.S. Pushkin’s “The Captain’s Daughter” has been included in the school curriculum for almost a century. Currently, in schools with Russian as the language of instruction in the Kyrgyz Republic, the story “The Captain's Daughter” is studied using the textbook for the eighth grade by G.I. Belenky, which was originally published in 1993. When writing our work, we used a textbook for the Kyrgyz school, authored by Z.S. Smelkova and K.Kh. Dzhideev, as well as school programs of G.I. Belenky, A.G. Kutuzova, T.F. Kurdyumova, L.A. Sheiman. [2. p. 95].

In traditional school teaching, analysis of a story often comes down to only reading and commenting on the text chapter by chapter. Next, students work on compiling characteristics of the characters. As a rule, this is a characteristic of one of the characters according to a previously given or collectively drawn up plan, which reproduces what was discussed in the lesson. The analysis ends with written

work - an essay. This sequence of lessons does not allow us to focus on the most significant ideas of the work or focus on the characters' characters as a whole. Students' thoughts are dormant; they do not develop the skill of independently analyzing a work, since all conclusions are presented to them in a ready-made form. And although in students' oral statements and essays there are clear answers to the main questions of the topic, although in general lessons it may seem to an outside observer that the children in this class know literature well, the students' knowledge is still of a formal nature. With this method of work, the main thing is lost - the aesthetic impact of the work on the student, without which, of course, literary development is impossible. [3. p. 112].

“In an article devoted to the analysis of the story, methodologist M.N. Saltykova comes to the conclusion that, when establishing the sequence of lessons for analyzing a story, we must proceed primarily from its artistic originality. “This uniqueness,” writes the author, “makes it impractical to study “The Captain’s Daughter” as the action develops, due to the presence of two plot lines in the story”. One cannot but agree with this conclusion. The methodologist suggests analyzing the story “in chapter cycles,” using the method of commented reading. This system of lessons has an advantage over the common chapter-by-chapter analysis: during the lesson, students cover a larger “area” of the text, which provides significant opportunities for comparison and reference to already studied material. Working with chapter cycles allows you to increase the proportion of students’ independent work. And yet, the system proposed by M.N. Saltykova is based on the principle she rejected - to analyze the story “as the action develops.” A number of lessons do not have a leading, central theme. This deprives the lesson of the necessary solidity and composure, especially when it is necessary to holistically analyze the characters’ characters.

In the article “The Tale of A.S. Pushkin “The Captain's Daughter” in School Study,” another methodologist A. Degozhskaya offers her following sequence of lessons for studying the story.

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